

Original research**Prevalence of comorbidity and polypharmacy among hospitalized elderly patients****Mustafa A. Alssageer***, Esraa S. Mohammed, Soaad A. Abd-Alsalm

Department of Pharmacology and Clinical Pharmacy, Faculty of Pharmacy, Sebha University, Sebha, Libya

*Corresponding author: mus.alhudiri@sebhau.edu.ly
<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-1139-0764>**Received:** 20-02-2022, **Revised:** 08-03-2022, **Accepted:** 12-03-2022, **Published:** 31-03-2022**Copyright:** Copyright© 2022 Alssageer et al. This is an open access article distributed under the **Creative Commons Attribution License**, which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original work is properly cited.**HOW TO CITE THIS:** *Alssageer et al. (2022) Prevalence of comorbidity and polypharmacy among hospitalized elderly patients. Mediterr J Pharm Pharm Sci. 2 (1): 55-64. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.0000000>*

Abstract: Aging seldom comes alone and it is considered to be the major factor for many diseases and comorbidities and disabilities. The objectives of the study are to examine demographic characteristics and prevalence of comorbidities and polypharmacy of elderly patients who were admitted at Sebha Medical Center according to the selected period. This study is descriptive and retrospective cross-sectional study conducted in Sebha during 2021. From 195 participants of the study, the highest rate of patients was from the age group of 65 - 74 years which accounted for 86 participants (44%) and followed by those age group of 75 - 84 years which was reported by 65 participants (33%). The majority of elderly patients have hypertension, (n = 116, 59%) and over one-third of the patients (n = 73, 37%) have diabetes mellitus while nearly one-quarter of patients have both diseases at the same time (n = 47, 24%). Nearly, three-quarters of patients have electrolytes imbalance (n = 142, 72%). Nearly, two-thirds of the patients had three to five comorbidity diseases (n = 122, 63%). Whereas, over one-third of the patients had just one or two comorbidities (n = 70, 36%). Almost all the participants have polypharmacy (n = 187, 96%). Just above half of the patients have five - ten medications (n = 100, 51%) compared with 45% of the patients from those who have more than ten medications (n = 87). This study showed that there is a strong relationship between the prevalence of polypharmacy and the number of comorbidities. A Spearman correlation test indicated that rate of comorbidities was related to polypharmacy with a significant correlation ($P < 0.01$). The present study found high prevalence of comorbidities and polypharmacy among elderly inpatients. Based on this high prevalence, practicing pharmaceutical care could play an effective role to reduce the risk of inappropriate polypharmacy among hospitalized elderly patients through encouraging clinical pharmacist to engage in clinical activities in hospitals.

Keywords: Clinical pharmacy, elderly patients, hospital, Libya, pharmacist**Introduction**

Population of elders is rapidly increasing in many countries in the world. The global share of older people increased from 09% in 1990 to 12% in 2013 and is expected to reach 21% by 2050 [1]. In the

same way, the life expectancy of the people was also raised. In 1950, the life expectancy in developed countries was 65 years while in developing countries was 42 years. Currently, however, life expectancy is

78 years in the developed world and 68 years in the developing world [2]. Aging seldom comes alone and it considered to be the major factor for many diseases, comorbidity, disability, frailty and social isolation [3]. Therefore, aging as an established risk factor for the development of comorbidity, disability and frailty as well as increasing health and pharmaceutical spending. In the same line, for hospital admission rate, need of intensive care, return visits and length of Emergency Department stay are higher for elderly patients than for younger patients [4].

The elderly population in Libya has increased nearly doubled over the last 20 years [5]. Older persons comprise 12% of the U.S. population, they account for 34% of all prescription drug expenditures [5]. Particularly for the treatment of chronic diseases, elderly patients were found to use about three times more drugs than younger patients [6]. Polypharmacy is often a consequence of multiple chronic conditions which may create a concern to physicians and it exposes the elderly patients to the effect beyond the beneficial patient outcome, thus, increasing the risk adverse drug reactions, drug-drug interactions and as consequence increase risk of disability, hospitalization and mortality [7]. However, the use of multiple drug treatments can be clinically appropriate if they improve health and quality of life [8]. In most of the literatures, polypharmacy defined as the regular intake of five or more medicines [9]. Elderly people in developing countries such as Libya have limited resources to access adequate medical care and shortage in some specialties which include geriatrics or physicians trained in geriatric medicine. Therefore, the objectives of this study are to examine demographic characteristics and prevalence of comorbidities and polypharmacy of elderly Libyan patients who were admitted at hospital according to the selected period.

Materials and methods

This study is descriptive and retrospective cross-sectional study conducted at Sebha Medical Centre (largest University hospital in south region of Libya) in 2021. It is used a non-probability convenient sampling technique to select the sample from who fulfill the inclusion criteria were enrolled. Patient records were eligible for inclusion if the patient's age is 65 years and above. Patients with more than 24 hours of length of stay in the hospital were included. Letter of ethical clearance was obtained from the ethical review committee of Sebha University (1/2021), after getting the official letter for permission from the faculty of pharmacy, permission also obtained from Sebha Medical Center (SMC) office for cooperation from Department of Medical Record at SMC.

Two independent researchers retrieved the documentation of the medication review from the medical records. We used a standardized data extraction sheet to collect relevant information from patient medical records and data will collected by trained pharmacy students using pre-tested data collection checklist.

Statistical analysis: Data from the recorded collection sheet were classified and coded. All collected data were feed into the computer and tabulated by using Microsoft Excel and IBM Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS), version 20th of statistical software. The categorical and the nominal variables were used for dependence and independence variables and were expressed as frequency and percentage. Descriptive statistics expressed as number, average and percentages. Correlation coefficient was tested by Spearman correlation test.

Results

During four months of collecting data, out of 1000 patient files, 195 elderly patients' files met the inclusion criteria (20%). **Table 1** shows that the highest rate of patients was from age group of 65 - 74 years old which accounted for 44% (n = 86) and followed by those age group of 75 - 84 years which was reported by 65 patients (33%). From 195

participants of the study, the majority of elderly patients have hypertension (n = 116, 59%) and over one-third of the patients have diabetes mellitus (n = 73, 37%) while nearly one-quarter of the patients have both diseases at the same time (n = 47, 24%). Nearly, three-quarter of the patients have electrolytes imbalance (n = 142, 72%) whereas female patients which accounted for 81% (n = 75) compared with male patients (n = 67, 67%).

Table 1: Demographic characteristics of elderly patients with comorbidity and polypharmacy rate

Gender	Male	Female	Total
Age (years)			
65 - 74	(47%) 48	(41%) 38	(44%) 86
75 - 84	(30%) 31	(36%) 34	(33%) 65
85 ≤	(23%) 23	(23%) 21	(22%) 44
Total	(52%) 102	(48%) 93	(100%) 195
comorbidity rate			
Comorbidity	Male	Female	Total
3 - 5	(59%) 60	(66%) 62	(63%) 122
1 - 2	(40%) 41	(31%) 29	(36%) 70
> 5	(01%) 01	(02%) 02	(02%) 03
Total	(52%) 102	(47.6%) 93	195
Polypharmacy			
Polypharmacy	Male	Female	Total
< 5	(05%) 05	(03%) 03	(04%) 08
5 - 10	(54%) 55	(48%) 45	(51%) 100
> 10	(41%) 42	(48%) 45	(45%) 87
Total	(52%) 102	(47.6%) 93	195

As shown in **Table 2** and **Figure 1**, nearly half of the patients have anemia (48.7%). To a less extent, infectious and heart disease were reported in 73 and 68 patients (37% and 34%), respectively. Regarding difference in gender, female patients who have heart diseases were nearly as double as the male patients which accounted for 42 and 26 patients (45% and 35%), respectively. However, the lowest rate was reported for cardiovascular disease which accounted for 31.7% of the patients. Based on results in the **Table 1**, illustrate that the most of the patients in this study sample suffer from

multi-morbidity. It shows that nearly the two third of them had (n = 122, 63.0%) from three to five comorbidity diseases in the same time. Whereas over one third of patients had just one or two comorbidities (n = 70, 36%). Regarding to the polypharmacy (**Table 1** and **Figure 2**), almost all elderly patients have polypharmacy (n = 187, 96.0%). Just above half of patients (100, 51%) have from 5 - 10 medications compared with 87, 45.0% from those have more than 10 medications. However, just eight patients (04.0%) take less than five medicines.

Table 2: Comorbidity among Libyan elderly patients

Comorbidity	Male	Female	Total
Electrolyte	(66%) 67	(81%) 75	(72%) 142
Hypertension	(56%) 58	(62%) 58	(59%) 116
Anemia	(49%) 50	(48%) 45	(49%) 95
Diabetes mellitus	(37%) 38	(39%) 36	(38%) 74
Infection	(34%) 35	(41%) 38	(37%) 73
Heart disease	(25%) 26	(45%) 42	(35%) 68
Cardiovascular disease	(35%) 36	(28%) 26	(32%) 62
Hypertension and diabetes mellitus	(24%) 24	(25%) 23	(24%) 47
Total	(52.0%) 102	(47.6%) 93	195

Patients may have more than one comorbidity

The results of **Table 3** show that there is a relationship between prevalence of polypharmacy and number of comorbidity. A Spearman correlation test indicated that the number of comorbidity is related to polypharmacy with a high significant level

($P < 0.01$). In the same way, polypharmacy have affected by difference in gender. A Spearman's test showed that a very high significant difference of prevalence of polypharmacy between both genders with $P < 0.01$.

Polypharmacy		Comorbidity			Total
		1 - 2	3 - 5	> 5	
< 5	Count	05	03	00	08
	Total %	2.6%	1.5%	0.0%	4.1%
5 - 10	Count	36	49	00	85
	Total %	18.6%	25.3%	0.0%	43.8%
> 10	Count	30	67	04	101
	Total %	15.5%	34.5%	02.1%	52.1%
Total	Counts	71	119	04	194
	Total (%)	36.6%	61.3%	02.1%	100%
Ordinal by ordinal	Spearman correlation	0.181	Significance = 0.01		

Discussion

In the present study, the average age found is 74.0 years old. It is slightly higher than that found in Lebanon and Iran studies which reported to be 72.5 and 72.6 years, respectively [10, 11]. Aging seldom comes alone and it considered to be a major factor for several diseases, comorbidity [3]. The presence of comorbidity also related to high consumption of medicines. Irrational medicine use is quite common, especially among elderly populations who have multiple comorbidities [12]. The present study shows that nearly two-thirds of patients had three to five comorbidity diseases at the same time. Similar trends in Dutch population found that patients with age ≥ 75 have multi-morbidity [13]. Multi-morbidity becomes progressively more common with age [14]. Also, in the present study, nearly three-quarters of patients have electrolytes imbalance and the highest rate was hyponatremia. This consists with present findings evidence showed that hyponatremia, is the most

common in hospitalized patients [15]. Hyponatremia, even when mild, is associated with increased mortality [16]. The risk of death during hospitalization is increased by double in patients admitted with hyponatremia compared with normonatremia [17]. Hyponatremia more likely common in elderly than hypernatremia [18 - 20]. This trend consistence with present study. Morbidity and mortality may be due to hyponatremia itself, or the inappropriate treatment of hyponatremia. Therefore, caution must be exercised to avoid inappropriate correction of the sodium imbalance, which could result in further complications, morbidity and death [21].

Abnormalities in potassium balance are common medical problems encountered among hospitalized patients [22]. Elderly is associated with an increased probability of developing hypokalemia during a hospital stay [23]. In our study, about 10% of elderly have hypokalemia compared to about 5% have

hyperkalemia. In agreement with present study, the prevalence rate of hypokalemia in hospitalized patients is between 05% and 20% [24 - 26] as in present study, 17.5%. In the same line, a descriptive cross-sectional study was conducted in a tertiary care center found that the prevalence of hypocalcemia in elderly [27]. In the elderly there is inadequate intestinal absorption of calcium combined with an age-related hormonal decline and vitamin D deficiency, which results in adverse effects on the calcium hemostasis [28]. Hypertension is age dependent and with the prolongation of life expectancy, affects more elderly people [29]. The majority of hypertension patients are not achieving their target blood pressure. Evidence shows that 40% of the patients had controlling blood pressure [30]. Ageing affects the clinical presentation of diabetes and accelerates diabetic related complications, alterations in the pharmacokinetics of insulin and oral medications affect individual drug choices and dosing decisions, making the diabetic management more complicated [31]. The presence of hypertension with diabetes increases risk of mortality by seven-fold [32] with a greater risk of death in developing nations [33]. Thus, about quarter of the Libyan elderly patients have concurrent diabetes mellitus with hypertension.

Anemia is highly prevalence in the elderly and this incidence increases with age [34]. The prevalence of anemia ranges from 40% in patients admitted to hospital, to the half in nursing home residents [35]. This is a quite similar rates that found nearly a half of Libyan patients have anemia. In adults aged 60 years and above, anemia has notable adverse consequences of impaired functionality, cognition, increased hospital admissions, and increased morbidity and mortality [36]. The higher prevalence in hospital-based studies is not surprising as it is well known that anemia is not uncommon finding in most disease states particularly patient with serious enough to necessitate hospital admission. Clinicians

may overlook anemia or attribute its symptoms to the underlying disease process.

Elderly generally has greater vulnerability to infections than younger adults since aging is associated with immune dysfunction [37]. Immune aging is associated with declining protective immunity combined with increasing incidence of inflammatory disease [38]. Comorbidity most often results in reduced innate immunity. In Turkey, infection is the most common cause of hospitalization among geriatric patients [39]. In present study, about 40% of elderly patients have infection. This higher rate could be related to difference in design of study since in our study we did not investigate the reasons of admission of the elderly into hospital.

The incidence of cerebrovascular diseases (CBVD) has raised-up by 100% in developing countries and it is the leading cause of continuous neurological disability in many countries [40]. With increasing age, the crude death rate of CBVD showed a fast growth [41]. A highly prevalent in persons with incident stroke, estimated at 89% for those aged ≥ 65 years and 60% for those aged < 65 years [42]. Currently, about 30% of elderly patients who admitted have a comorbidity cerebrovascular accident (CVA) disease. This a lower rate of prevalence compared the other studies in literature could be related to characteristics the population of our study which was restricted only on hospitalized elderly patients. According to the latest WHO report, stroke deaths in Libya was about 10% of total deaths (WHO, 2018). Thus, the incidence of CVA is high in South Libya and the stroke has revealed a high incidence rate of 662 per 100,000 deaths per year with morality rate was about 25% within 30-days case [43].

The prevalence of polypharmacy is increasing, owing largely to changes in population demographics and increasing multi-morbidity.

Individuals using at least five prescription medicines amplified by 70% as compared to the last decade [44]. Elderly patients who suffering from multimorbidity they usually need multi-medications to manage their comorbidities which inherently increases the risk of polypharmacy. The present study revealed that a significant correlation between comorbidity and polypharmacy and almost all elderly patients have polypharmacy. Previous studies have shown a similarly high prevalence polypharmacy in other countries. In Saudi Arabia and Germany polypharmacy was found in 90% of the patients [45, 46]. Polypharmacy may create a concern to clinicians it exposes the elderly patients to the effect beyond the beneficial patient outcome [7]. A systematic review noted that polypharmacy has a clearly established strong relationship with negative clinical outcomes [47]. Cohort Korean study found that polypharmacy is associated with increased risk of mortality in the elderly [48] as well as a greater risk of hospitalization [49] and death [48]. However, the use of multiple drug treatments

can be clinically appropriate if they improve health and quality of life [8]. Best approaches towards appropriate polypharmacy should address over- as well as under-treatment in older patients.

Clinical pharmacists with their extensive knowledge and training in pharmacotherapy and pharmacokinetics can play a crucial role in the management of chronic diseases through their engagement with other healthcare staff in pharmacotherapy interventions and preventing the harmful consequences of polypharmacy.

Conclusion: Prevalence of comorbidity and polypharmacy among elderly inpatients is high. Practicing of pharmaceutical care may play an effective role to reduce risk of inappropriate polypharmacy among hospitalized elderly patients through encourage the clinical pharmacists to engage in the clinical activities in the hospitals? It also is urgent needed establishment of therapeutic local guidelines based on evidence-based medicine at Libyan hospitals and implemented them in elderly treatment.

Conflict of interest: The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

Author contributions: Alssageer M: Conceived, design of study, editing and revising the manuscript. Mohammed ES: Collect and analysis of data and preparing first draft of the manuscript. Abd Alsalm SA: Collect and analysis of data and preparing first draft of the manuscript. All authors approved final version of the manuscript.

Data availability statement: The data that support the findings of this study are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

Ethical issues: Including plagiarism, informed consent, data fabrication or falsification and double publication or submission have completely been observed by authors.

Author declarations: We confirm all relevant ethical guidelines have been followed and any necessary IRB and/or ethics committee approvals have been obtained.

References

1. United Nations (2013). Department of Economic and Social Affairs, Population Division. World Population Ageing 2013. ST/ESA/SER.A/348. United Nations, New York, publication.
2. Divo MJ, Martinez CH, Mannino DM (2014) Ageing and the epidemiology of multimorbidity. *European Respiratory Journal*. 4 (4): 1055-1068. doi:10.1183/09031936.00059814.
3. Christensen K, Doblhammer G, Rau R, Vaupel JW (2009) Ageing populations: the challenges ahead. *Lancet* (London, England). 374 (9696): 1196-1208. doi:10.1016/S0140-6736(09)61460-4.
4. Samaras N, Chevalley T, Samaras D, Gold G (2010) Older patients in the emergency department: a review. *Annals of Emergency Medicine*. 56 (3): 261-269. doi:10.1016/j.annemergmed.2010.04.015.
5. Nabalamba A, Chikoko M (2011) Aging population challenges in Africa. African Development Bank. AFDP. Chief Economist Complex. 1 (1): 1-19.
6. Vinks THAM, de Koning FHP, de Lange TM, Egberts TCG (2006) Identification of potential drug-related problems in the elderly: The role of the community pharmacist. *Pharmacy World and Science*. 28 (1): 33-38. doi:10.1007/s11096-005-4213-4.
7. Scott IA, Hilmer SN, Reeve E, Polter K, Le Couteur D, Rigby D, Gnjdic D, Del Mar CB, Roughead EE, Page A, Jansen J, Martin JH (2015) Reducing inappropriate polypharmacy: The process of deprescribing. *Journal of the American Medical Association Internal Medicine*. 175 (5): 827-834. doi:10.1001/jamainternmed.2015.0324.
8. Duerden M, Payne R, Avery T (2013) Polypharmacy and Medicines Optimisation. King's Fund Report, November 2013. 2013. doi:10.13140/RG.2.1.1597.0726.
9. Hovstadius B, Hovstadius K, Astrand B, Petersson G (2010) Increasing polypharmacy - an individual-based study of the Swedish population 2005-2008. *BMC Clinical Pharmacology*. 10: 16. doi:10.1186/1472-6904-10-16.
10. Saab YB, Hachem A, Sinno S, El-Moalem H (2006) Inappropriate medication use in elderly Lebanese outpatients: Prevalence and risk factors. *Drugs Aging*. 23 (9): 743-752. doi:10.2165/00002512-200623090-00004.
11. Azoulay L, Zargarzadeh A, Salahshouri Z, Oraichi D, Bérard A (2005) Inappropriate medication prescribing in community-dwelling elderly people living in Iran. *European Journal of Clinical Pharmacology*. 61 (12): 913-919. doi:10.1007/s00228-005-0036-4.
12. Fick DM, Mion LC, Beers MH, L Waller J (2008) Health outcomes associated with potentially inappropriate medication use in older adults. *Research in Nursing and Health*. 31 (1): 42-51. doi:10.1002/nur.20232.
13. van Oostrom SH, Picavet HSJ, van Gelder BM, Lemmens LC, Hoeyman N, van Dijk CE, Verheij RA, Schellevis FG, Baan CA (2012) Multimorbidity and comorbidity in the Dutch population - data from general practices. *BMC Public Health*. 12: 715. doi:10.1186/1471-2458-12-715.
14. van den Akker M, Vaes B, Goderis G, Van Pottelbergh G, De Burghgraeve T, Henrard S. (2019) Trends in multimorbidity and polypharmacy in the Flemish-Belgian population between 2000 and 2015. *PLoS One*. 14 (2): e0212046. doi:10.1371/journal.pone.0212046.
15. Spasovski G, Vanholder R, Allolio B, Annane D, Ball S, Bichet D, Beaux G, Fenske W, Hoorn EJ, Ichai C, Joannidis M, Soupart A, Zietse R, Haller M, Der Veer S, Bessen WU, Nagler E (2014) Clinical practice guideline on diagnosis and treatment of hyponatraemia. *Nephrology Dialysis Transplantation*. 29 (S2): i1-i39. doi:10.1093/ndt/gfu040.
16. Waikar SS, Mount DB, Curhan GC (2009) Mortality after hospitalization with mild, moderate, and severe hyponatremia. *American Journal of Medicine*. 122 (9): 857-865. doi:10.1016/j.amjmed.2009.01.027.
17. Zilberberg MD, Exuzides A, Spalding J, Foreman A, Jones Ag, Colby C, Shorr AF (2008) Epidemiology, clinical and economic outcomes of admission hyponatremia among hospitalized patients. *Current Medical Research and Opinion*. 24 (6): 1601-1608. doi:10.1185/03007990802081675.
18. Liamis G, Rodenburg EM, Hofman A, Zietse R, Stricker BH, Hoorn EJ (2013) Electrolyte disorders in community subjects: prevalence and risk factors. *American Journal of Medicine*. 126 (3): 256-263. doi:10.1016/j.amjmed.2012.06.037.
19. Hawkins RC (2003) Age and gender as risk factors for hyponatremia and hypernatremia. *Clinica Chimica Acta*. 337 (1-2): 169-172. doi:10.1016/j.cccn.2003.08.001.
20. Arampatzis S, Frauchiger B, Fiedler G-M, Leichtle AB, Buhl D, Schwar ZC, Funk GC, Zimmermann H,

- Exadaktylos AK, Lindner G (2012) Characteristics, symptoms, and outcome of severe dysnatremias present on hospital admission. *American Journal of Medicine*. 125 (11): 1125.e1-1125.e7. doi:10.1016/j.amjmed.2012.04.041.
21. Rose BD and TWP (2001) *Clinical physiology of acid-base and electrolyte disorders*. 5th ed. McGraw Hill Medical Publishing Division; 2001.
 22. Palaka E, Grandy S, Darlington O, McEwan P, van Doornewaard A (2020) Associations between serum potassium and adverse clinical outcomes: A systematic literature review. *International Journal of Clinical Practice*. 74 (1): e13421. doi:10.1111/ijcp.13421.
 23. Zuccalà G, Pedone C, Cocchi A, Pahor M, Carosella L, Carbonin P, Bernabei R (2000) Older age and in-hospital development of hypokalemia from loop diuretics: results from a multicenter survey. GIFA Investigators. Multicenter Italian Pharmacoepidemiologic Study Group. *The Journal of Gerontology: Series A, Biological Sciences and Medical Sciences*. 55 (4): M232-8. doi:10.1093/gerona/55.4.m232.
 24. Paice BJ, Paterson KR, Onyanga-Omara F, Donnelly T, Gray JM, Lawson DH (1986) Record linkage study of hypokalaemia in hospitalized patients. *Postgraduate Medical Journal*. 62 (725): 187-191. doi:10.1136/pgmj.62.725.187.
 25. Crop MJ, Hoorn EJ, Lindemans J, Zietse R (2007) Hypokalaemia and subsequent hyperkalaemia in hospitalized patients. *Nephrology Dialysis Transplantation*. 22 (12): 3471-3477. doi:10.1093/ndt/gfm471.
 26. Eliacik E, Yildirim T, Sahin U, Kizilaoslanoglu C, Tapan U, Aybal-Kutlugun A, Hascelik G, Arici M (2015) Potassium abnormalities in current clinical practice: frequency, causes, severity and management. *Medical Principles and Practice*. 24 (3): 271-275. doi:10.1159/000376580.
 27. Thapa S, Rayamajhi RJ (2020) Hypocalcemia in elderly population in a tertiary care hospital: a descriptive cross-sectional study. *Journal of Nepal Medical Association*. 58 (231): 843-846. doi:10.31729/jnma.5324.
 28. Veldurthy V, Wei R, Oz L, Dhawan P, Jeon YH, Christakos S (2016) Vitamin D, calcium homeostasis and aging. *Bone Research*. 4: 16041. doi:10.1038/boneres.2016.41.
 29. Fagard RH (2002) Epidemiology of hypertension in the elderly. *American Journal of Geriatr Cardiology*. 11 (1): 23-28. doi:10.1111/j.1076-7460.2002.00856.x.
 30. Jaddou HY, Batiha AM, Khader YS, Kanaan AH, El-Khateeb MS, Ajlouni KM (2011) Hypertension prevalence, awareness, treatment and control, and associated factors: results from a national survey, Jordan. *International Journal of Hypertenion*. 2011: 828797. doi:10.4061/2011/828797.
 31. Inamdar SZ KR (2016) Drug related problems in elderly patients with type 2 diabetes mellitus. *Journal of Diabetology*. 7 (1): 1.
 32. Vlado Perkovic, Sunil V Badve GLB (2022) Treatment of diabetic kidney disease. Uptodate. <https://www.uptodate.com/contents/treatment-of-diabetic-kidney-disease#disclaimerContent>. Published February 9, 2022.
 33. Awoke A, Awoke T, Alemu S, Megabiaw B (2012) Prevalence and associated factors of hypertension among adults in Gondar, Northwest Ethiopia: a community based cross-sectional study. *BMC Cardiovascular Disorders*. 12: 113. doi:10.1186/1471-2261-12-113.
 34. Ania BJ, Suman VJ, Fairbanks VF, Melton LJ (1994) Prevalence of anemia in medical practice: community versus referral patients. *Mayo Clinic Proceedings*. 69 (8): 730-735. doi:10.1016/s0025-6196(12)61089-1.
 35. Gaskell H, Derry S, Andrew Moore R, McQuay HJ (2008) Prevalence of anaemia in older persons: systematic review. *BMC Geriatrics*. 8: 1. doi:10.1186/1471-2318-8-1.
 36. Ershler WB (2019) Unexplained Anemia in the Elderly. *Clinics in Geriatric Medicine*. 35 (3): 295-305. doi:10.1016/j.cger.2019.03.002.
 37. Ben-Yehuda A, Weksler ME (1992) Host resistance and the immune system. *Clinics in Geriatric Medicine*. 8 (4): 701-711.
 38. Frasca D, Blomberg BB (2016) Inflammaging decreases adaptive and innate immune responses in mice and humans. *Biogerontology*. 17 (1): 7-19. doi:10.1007/s10522-015-9578-8.
 39. Kurtaran B, Kuscu F, Korkmaz P, Ozdemir B, Inan D, Oztoprak V, Ozatag DM, Dagli O, Birengel S, Ozdemir K (2020) A snapshot of geriatric infections in Turkey: ratio of geriatric inpatients in hospitals and evaluation of their infectious diseases: A multicenter point prevalence study. *International Journal of Infectious Diseases*. 100: 337-342. doi:10.1016/j.ijid.2020.08.046.
 40. Feigin VL, Lawes CMM, Bennett DA, Barker-Collo SL, Parag V (2009) Worldwide stroke incidence and early case fatality reported in 56 population-based studies: A systematic review. *Lancet Neurology*. 8 (4): 355-369. doi:10.1016/S1474-4422(09)70025-0.

41. He J, Gu D, Wu X, et al. (2005) Major causes of death among men and women in China. *The New England Journal of Medicine*. 353 (11): 1124-1134. doi:10.1056/NEJMsa050467.
42. Yousufuddin M, Bartley AC, Alsawas M, et al. (2017) Impact of multiple chronic conditions in patients hospitalized with stroke and transient ischemic attack. *Journal of Stroke and Cerebrovascular Diseases*. 26 (6): 1239-1248. doi:10.1016/j.jstrokecerebrovasdis.2017.01.015.
43. Ahmed MG, Ali MH, Sufrani AM, Shenib FA, Musbah ANM (2003) Stroke in South Libya. *Sebha University of Journal Medical Sciences*. 3 (1): 22-26.
44. Gu Q, Dillon CF, Burt VL (2021) Prescription drug use continues to increase: U.S. prescription drug data for 2007-2008. *National Center for Health Statistics - Data Briefs*. (42): 1-8. PMID: 20854747.
45. Bamagous GA (2020) Patterns of prescription and inappropriate medications use in elderly patients of Makkah community in Saudi Arabia. *African Journal of Pharmacy and Pharmacology*. 14 (11): 386-394. doi:https://doi.org/10.5897/AJPP2020.5191.
46. Schneider J, Algharably EAE, Budnick A, Wenzel A, Dräger D, Kreutz R (2021) High prevalence of multimorbidity and polypharmacy in elderly patients with chronic pain receiving home care are associated with multiple medication-related problems. *Frontiers in Pharmacology*. 12: 686990. doi:10.3389/fphar.2021.686990.
47. Maher RL, Hanlon J, Hajjar ER (2014) Clinical consequences of polypharmacy in elderly. *Expert Opinion on Drug Safety*. 13 (1): 57-65. doi:10.1517/14740338.2013.827660.
48. Cheong SJ, Yoon JL, Choi SH, Kim MY, Cho JJ, Ju YS (2016) The effect of polypharmacy on mortality in the elderly. *Korean Journal of Family Practice*. 6 (6): 643-650. doi:10.21215/kjfp.2016.6.6.643.
49. Wastesson JW, Morin L, Tan ECK, Johnell K (2018) An update on the clinical consequences of polypharmacy in older adults: a narrative review. *Expert Opinion on Drug Safety*. 17 (12): 1185-1196. doi:10.1080/14740338.2018.1546841.